

The “Black Boy Crisis” of the Mid-1960s: Social Science Research on Poverty and the “Moynihan Problem” That Still Resonate

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Abstract:

This article will treat the Moynihan Report as revealing the real Achilles’s heel of mid-1960s liberalism – its paternalistic and hetero-normative notions about the nuclear family. Rather than analyzing the Report itself, I will try and provide a glimpse into how Moynihan’s gendered assumptions found its way into his writing. What I will argue is, as a typical Cold War liberal intellectual, and politician, he found readily available material in mid-1960s social scientific knowledge, to substantiate his gendered claims. The plight of the young urban black male, as ready-made ingredient for social chaos, was almost always the underlying theme in the studies that he chose to rely on – even when such studies had a structural, and not necessarily cultural, approach to poverty. Within this context, the article will also dwell on the relationship between social scientific research on poverty and policy implementation.

Keywords: Moynihan Report, Culture of Poverty, Black Boy Crisis, Gender and Family, Racial Liberalism

1960'ların Ortasındaki 'Siyah Erkek Çocuk Krizi': Yoksulluk Üzerine Sosyal Bilim Araştırmaları ve Hâlâ Yankı Bulan 'Moynihan Sorunu'

Öz

Bu makale, Moynihan Raporu'nu, 1960'ların ortalarındaki liberalizmin gerçek Aşıl topuğunu — çekirdek aileye ilişkin paternalist ve heteronormatif varsayımlarını — açığa çıkaran bir metin olarak ele almaktadır. Raporun kendisini doğrudan analiz etmekten ziyade, Moynihan'ın toplumsal cinsiyet temelli varsayımlarının yazılarına nasıl yansıdığına dair bir bakış sunmayı amaçlamaktadır. Bu çalışmada savunulan temel argüman şudur: Soğuk Savaş döneminin tipik bir liberal entelektüeli ve siyasetçisi olarak Moynihan, toplumsal cinsiyete dayalı iddialarını temellendirmek için 1960'ların ortasındaki sosyal bilimsel bilgi birikimi içinde kolaylıkla erişilebilen malzemeler bulmuştur. Kentli genç siyah erkeğin durumu, toplumsal kaosun hazır bir unsuru olarak, onun başvurduğu çalışmaların neredeyse tamamında örtük bir tema olarak yer almaktadır — bu çalışmalar yoksulluğa kültürel değil daha çok yapısal bir yaklaşım benimsemiş olsa bile. Bu bağlamda makale, yoksulluk üzerine sosyal bilimsel araştırmalar ile politika uygulamaları arasındaki ilişkiyi de incelemektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Moynihan Raporu, Yoksulluk Kültürü, Siyahi Erkek Çocuk Krizi, Toplumsal Cinsiyet ve Aile, Irksal Liberalizm

The “Black Boy Crisis” of The Mid-1960s Social Science Research on Poverty and the “Moynihan Problem” That Still Resonates¹

In all inner-city neighborhoods... there is a problem minority...that comes largely from the disconnected youth between ages 16 and 24. Most are not in school and are chronically out of work... Many belong to gangs. Their street or thug culture is real...all inflected with a threatening vision of blackness openly embraced as the thug life. Such street culture is simply the black urban version of one of America's most iconic traditions: the Wild West.

Orlando Patterson
The New York Times
(Patterson, 2015, May 9)

1 The terms “black boy crisis” and “Moynihan Problem,” are borrowed from historian Malinda A. Lindquist, and political scientist Sanford F. Schram, respectively.

Orlando Patterson, a Harvard sociologist, wrote the above quoted opinion piece, in the immediate aftermath of the subsiding of the unrest in Baltimore, Maryland, triggered by the events in which a young black man lost his life due to police violence.² According to Patterson, defining the problem only in terms of racism and police violence would be an oversimplification. What he called for was, what *The New Yorker* staff writer Kelefa Sanneh called, a redemption of the culturalist tradition, and “thereby... [of] sociology itself.” As Sanneh noted, Patterson had “argued that ‘fearful’ sociologists had abandoned ‘studies of the cultural dimensions of poverty, particularly black poverty,’ and that the discipline had become ‘largely irrelevant’” (Sanneh, 2015). Sanneh wrote his opinion piece to comment on a new anthology edited by Patterson (with Ethan Fosse) called *The Cultural Matrix: Understanding Black Youth* (Patterson & Fosse, 2015) According to Sanneh, the anthology “is meant to show that the culturalist tradition still has something to teach us... on the fiftieth anniversary of its most important predecessor” – The Moynihan Report (Sanneh, 2015).

2 This was part of a series of protests in several cities that were initiated back in 2014 in response to the shooting of Michael Brown, and have continued to this day with the crystallization of the Black Lives Matter movement.

Patterson's plea in this *The New York Times* piece, can be seen as reminiscent of a revival of the language, in the twenty first century social sciences, of what historian Malinda A. Lindquist referred to as the "black boy crisis" Lindquist had designated the mid-1960s publication of the Moynihan Report, as the turning point that epitomized the peak for the surfacing of such social scientific language, at a time when a national effort was declared to fight a newly "discovered" and peculiar kind of poverty (Lindquist, 2012, p. 152). It was in the post-war era, that there was a crisis-ridden language on black men and boys among social scientists. Starting with Abram Kardiner and Lionel Ovesey's *Mark of Oppression* (1951) and Frazier's later work *The Black Bourgeoisie* (1957), "a gendered argument [was added on]to a class based perspective on socialization," and with John Rohrer and Edmonson's *The Eighth Generation Grows Up: Cultures and Personalities of New Orleans Negroes* (1960), "the tide had fully turned" (Lindquist, 2012, p. 162) and gender emerged as the defining feature and organizing category of analysis on African American families. All these works signaled the psychological turn that blamed black middle and lower class mothers – the former for "marking their sons" and the latter for "dominating and abusing their husbands" (Lindquist, 2012, pp. 168–170). Moynihan Report's publication was, according to Lindquist, the peak of such line of scientific work. In what Lindquist called the "Moynihan effect," the policy solutions such as a placing young black men either in military institutions or into "loving white middle-class homes" eventually shaped a broader policy discussion and implementation into the decade. Moynihan's intention on using his argument for advancing a major federal jobs program, led to such policies as, "local and national fatherhood initiatives to teenage pregnancy prevention programs to an assortment of job training programs that focus on imparting soft skills – such as interview techniques and wardrobe advice

– to black youth, in order to make them a more attractive workforce to white employers." (Lindquist, 2012, pp. 183–184)

Such language, had fallen into disfavor fifty years ago, after the controversy surrounding the Moynihan Report, until it was recently revived by both scholars like Patterson calling out for bringing the culture back into the analysis, and by scholars such as Michael B. Katz, Sanford F. Schram, and Alice O'Connor, all of whom stood at varying points of caution on such an approach (Katz, 2013; O'Connor, 2002; Schram, 2002, 2005; Soss et al., 2011). Amounting to what Sanford F. Schram dubbed the "Moynihan Problem," which was the risk of being associated with the controversy, many of the mainstream sociologists and anthropologists increasingly moved towards structural explanations in poverty research (Schram, 2005, pp. 261–262). Katz also complained that, by not being able to replace culture with another meaningful category of analysis, sociologists and anthropologists, since then, have "marginal[ized] their disciplines among policy makers and facilitate[d] the passage of leadership in poverty research to the economists." (Katz, 2013, p. 56) This, according to Katz, was one reason for the way conservative social scientific and political interpretations took over the culture of poverty thesis, and beginning with the conservative ascendancy in the 1980s, displaced discussions over poverty by the issue of welfare dependency. That was why, as Katz (2013) noted, "not long after Moynihan's 2003 death, the Moynihan Report staged a stunning comeback, refurbishing Moynihan's reputation as prescient and a seer." (pp. 66–67)³.

In the resulting discussions around both the use of culture as an analytical tool for poverty research and the questions concerning the proper relationship between social science and politics, political scientists Sanford F. Schram and Alice O'Connor raised important questions. Schram called for the need in social science for avoiding the tendency to "whitewash"

³ Earliest such work trying to absolve culture from blaming the victim, balance of culture and structure, was William Julius Wilson's *The Truly Disadvantaged* (1987) (and later his *More Than Just Race* (2009)). In 2009, *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* devoted a whole issue on Moynihan and the Report. See *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, Vol. 621, "The Moynihan Report Revisited: Lessons and Reflections after Four Decades" (Jan., 2009); In June 2013, The Urban Institute published a report entitled "The Moynihan Report Revisited," mostly calling for looking at the report for current problems. Greg Weiner's *American Burke: The Uncommon Liberalism of Daniel Patrick Moynihan* (USA, 2015) also sought to revive Moynihan's ideas and his political stance, which he defines as reminiscent of a "Burkean idealism," which he thought is the key ingredient missing from the American liberalism of today

racial disparities in the U.S. economy” and for being willing to take the risk that comes with the “Moynihan Problem” in a politically sensitive way, so that “understanding the racial dimensions of welfare can help promote racial justice (Schram, 2005, p. 262). In a way, Schram responded to O’Connor’s plea in her *Poverty Knowledge* (2002) for a more “methodologically diverse and politically engaged” approach in order to reverse the tendency in social science research on poverty in “becoming a highly technical field dominated by quantitative modeling grounded in economic reasoning” (Schram, 2002, pp. 110–111) In his *Praxis for the Poor* (2002), where he juxtaposed the kind of politically informed and activist social science research done by Frances Fox Piven and Richard Cloward, and the one done by Moynihan, Schram declared:

More than methodological diversity and political engagement, we need to invert the relationship of social science research to social welfare policy. We need to challenge the assumption that social science in theory precedes social welfare advocacy in practice. We need to challenge, therefore, the assumption that research is the foundation for policy, and that there is a logical order to things where thought comes first and action follows based on rational plans. (Schram, 2002, p. 111)

This article can be seen as an attempt in showing how there was not necessarily a “logical order to things” back in the mid-1960s as well. It aims to look into the origins of such questions, by looking at that historical moment in American intellectual and political history, which epitomized a very close interaction between the now seemingly separate areas of academia and policy-making. Taking the mid-1960s controversy surrounding the Moynihan Report as the anchor, however, this article will stretch the intellectual historical framework a bit further back to when Moynihan was contemplating on his work as the policy maker, and then, forward into the after-

math, to the times he prepared for a redemptive intellectual defense as the scholar working on his next but never published book, tentatively entitled *Toward Equality*.

eral scholars, including Lindquist, Susan Greenbaum and Robert O. Self, have already paid attention to the transformative powers inherent in that moment of the controversy, by paying close attention to the coming together of racialized and gendered notions (Lindquist, 2012; Greenbaum, 2015; Self, 2012). Just as Lindquist placed it in the midst of a shift in social scientific thinking about a "black boy crisis", Self placed it into a very important turning point in his account of the history of what he called "breadwinner liberalism." According to Self, Moynihan Report came at a historically critical moment, both for the federal government intent on fighting poverty and for a civil rights movement that was trying more harder than ever to push for equality on a socioeconomic footing – a moment which required "a combination of immense political capital, wide public support, compelling moral authority, and a committed national state." As Self noted, Moynihan's approach, "however unwittingly and unintentionally" ended up offering "an escape hatch from that difficult work ahead. [And] to accept a discussion at that historical moment on the terrain of moral and familial dysfunction was already to have lost the debate" (Self, 2012, Kindle Location 549). Finally, Daniel Geary, with his latest book analyzing the report and its inherently liberal and conservative potential and controversial nature, aimed at a "history without heroes and villains," putting less emphasis on the report's transformative moment, and more on the ways in which it epitomized and reflected the inherent contradictions of 1960s liberalism itself Unlike Self, Geary did not see the report as emblematic of a post-war liberal consensus that defined economic equality in terms of "family wage," but as revealing the "ideological diversity that predated the controversy" (Geary, 2015, p. 9).

Therefore, dwelling not so much on the actual time period when the report was publicized and hotly debated, this article aims to hold the magnifying glass to the intellectual context from within which Daniel Patrick Moynihan produced the document – in the manner, as Sanforn Schram (2002) defined, of “a ‘mass intellectual’... playing both ends against the middle [by using] his academic credentials to gain political influence and his political influencing to serve as the basis for his scholarly writings” (p. 59).⁴ By looking at the first instances in which Moynihan started interacting with the social scientific and academic circles for debating the ways in which the federal government could fight Lyndon B. Johnson’s newly announced War on Poverty; and then, at the kind of social science that he had at its disposal when he was working on his prospective book *Toward Equality*,⁵ this article aims to show how Moynihan Report’s legacy, rested not so much in its content or rhetoric, but more in the peculiar historical context in which its social science research had been done – a context that commanded an urgent solution to the perceived “black boy crisis” – and the peculiar way in which Moynihan “combined scholarship and politics in the halls of power” (Schram, 2002, p. 59). Thus, both because of the nature and content of the specific set of scholarship that Moynihan himself chose to process back then, and because it really was the utmost concern on the agenda of social scientists, policy makers, and civil rights activists alike; the main focus in this work, will remain on the various ways in which the condition of the black men was insistently problematized.

By combining intellectual and political history, this article ventures beyond a pro- or anti-Moynihan debate, shedding light instead on the discursive limitations of mid-century liberalism across the political spectrum. Methodologically, it employs an intensive and focused archival analysis of the Daniel P. Moynihan Papers at the Library of Congress, with a spe-

⁴ Here, the author would like to thank Daniel Geary, for his feedback on an earlier conference paper version of this article, which prompted further inquiry on the coming together of Moynihan’s scholarly and political identities.

⁵ *Toward Equality* was the title for the manuscript that he intended to publish, in defense of his report, after he left his post in the Johnson administration. His research for *Toward Equality*, would last roughly until his appointment to the Nixon administration. As Daniel Geary (2015) noted, having reentered politics, he would shelve the over 750 typescript pages to never be published (p. 180)

cific focus on the "poverty knowledge" Moynihan utilized, both while producing his controversial report and while preparing for his redemptive intellectual defense afterwards. Although the utilization of only a small portion of the collection might present as a limitation, it also makes possible a "magnifying glass" approach. Examining the internal government memoranda, personal correspondence with fellow social scientists, and, crucially, the marginalia and underlinings found in Moynihan's personal reading files (such as his copies of works by Harry Caudill and Edgar Auerswald); enables figures much less prominent than Moynihan and various anonymous writers of memoirs and press releases, to make their appearance at this crucial intersection of academia and "halls of power" in 1960s American social policy making history.

The methodology also incorporates a comparative historiographical lens, juxtaposing the dominant social scientific discourse of the era with those of scholar activists, critical sociologists, feminist and activist critiques, to expose the racialized and gendered norms that marginalized alternative sociological perspectives. Doubled with the specific time period from which this article draws its source material, this juxtaposition reveals the real Achilles's heel of mid-century liberalism: Even at a time when Moynihan's intent was seeking intellectual redemption from the controversy surrounding his report and diverting attention away from biological race toward structural socioeconomic variables, his dismissive stance towards and marginalization of such studies, ended up reinforcing those same racialized and gendered premises.

A New Kind of Poverty and a New Kind of Moynihanesque Structuralism

The kind of literature and research that was available to Moynihan presented him with varying ideas in the culturalist versus structuralist spectrum. As Geary noted, Moynihan ironically came out of the intellectual and political context of “racial liberalism’s socio-economic turn in the mid-1960s” (Geary, 2011, p. 55). Given the origins of the report from within this shift, it could have been unexpected that his work eventually wended up on the culturalist end. However, even while opting for structural and class-based explanations, as opposed to a racial one, most of the studies at his disposal seemed to be unable to venture beyond their gendered and sexualized assumptions, and thus, beyond the idea that there should be some kind of “subculture” to be rearranged in line with white middle class values. The subculture that scholars still attuned to lower classes, had the potential to be easily applied to the African American urban population towards the middle of the decade, as poverty had inflicted the urban black population in disproportionate rates. Most importantly, however, this application seemed to amplify the gendered aspects of the arguments, while downplaying the elements of race and class.

6 For this and all subsequent references to Daniel P. Moynihan Papers at the Manuscript Division, Library of Congress, Washington, DC., page numbers, when available, will be cited as they appear in the original documents.

One earliest and most clearly stated such resource in his possession, though undated and anonymous, was a memorandum entitled “Illegitimacy and Poverty in the United States: Some Basic facts and Considerations,” prepared in his own asking while he was already the Assistant Secretary of Labor for Policy Planning and Research.⁶ It was looking specifically at the relationship between illegitimacy and poverty. and presented a very strong case, throughout, about the difficulty in assessing the relationship between illegitimacy and racial make-up of the lower and middle classes. Mostly utilizing the works of Elizabeth Herzog of the Children’s Bureau, the memo also

summarized the arguments of such scholars as the family sociologist Clark E. Vincent, and that of the less mainstream scholars such as the Howard University sociologist Stanley K. Bigman. While doing this, it also paid attention to in depth case studies at the local level, to show the differing angles that were not so evident in the many of the government statistics that it also compiled ("Illegitimacy and Poverty," n.d.).

The document opened up with a clear warning on the impossibility of locating unwed motherhood as a phenomenon comfortably into a specific social, economic, religious or racial group. Noting that, although many unwed mothers, seemed to "fit the stereotype – poor, ignorant, promiscuous or, at least, put-upon," the contemporary knowledge began to shatter this stereotype, revealing new findings about more and more mothers ("Illegitimacy and Poverty," n.d., p. 1). Warning further that, "to define a societal condition as a 'social problem' [would imply] a judgment based on social values," it noted that any solutions to be offered to lessen illegitimacy in the United States would be "inevitably based on value judgments" ("Illegitimacy and Poverty," n.d., p. 2). The most important warning was about the distortions in the data available – a warning that was assembled mostly from the writings of Herzog, specifying especially the problematic classifications based on race ("Illegitimacy and Poverty," n.d., pp. 4–7).

Opting for a class-based explanation, both Herzog, and the memo quoted extensively from Clark E. Vincent. His *Unmarried Mothers* published in 1961 and an earlier one on the "ego involvement in sexual relations" had actually challenged the solely class-oriented explanations, in addition to casting doubt on the utility of race as a category. He had showed how "unwed motherhood is more prevalent among women of higher socio-economic status than had previously been suspected" and how it was not possible to talk about a single type of unwed mother, with many

variables within racial, cultural and socio-economic groups as well (“Illegitimacy and Poverty,” n.d., p. 19). In Herzog’s *Child Welfare* journal article, where she first noted the contemporary irrelevance of “the slavery specific culture thesis,” Vincent’s findings and similar investigations were the basis for the conclusion, that “neither a Negro culture nor an income level could be used as a tag to wipe away the need for looking closer” and explore into the existence of “these layers within layers – as well as their crucial significance” (“Illegitimacy and Poverty,” n.d., p. 22). Herzog, however, was noting the dominance of class variables even in such studies. In another study of the Child Welfare League of America, Vincent’s work was indeed the basis for a conclusion that challenged Franklin E. Frazier’s thesis in class terms. To challenge Frazier’s “historical base for a Negro subculture involving a matriarchal family structure with minimal value placed on legal marriage” the study noted Vincent’s study along with other studies of the ADC in Eastern cities, it declared: “It would be more profitable to think in terms of lower-class subculture rather than racial subculture” (“Illegitimacy and Poverty,” n.d., p. 26).

In almost all the studies that were in Moynihan’s possession from the era had this explicit othering of the lower class, most obvious of which was the classical work on Appalachia, *Night Comes to the Cumberlandds: A Biography of a Depressed Area* by Harry M. Caudill (Caudill, 1963). In the few xeroxed pages found in Moynihan’s files, the parts underlined by Moynihan, where welfare dependency and ADC’s alleged tendency to worsen both illegitimacy and family breakdown, were knit into a narrative of loose sexual mores. Although the story begins with the male family head losing the job he had started at the coal mine when he was seventeen, not being able to find a well enough paying job thereafter, and ending up in his mid-forties with unemployment benefits and food rations, it ends with a note saying that “as hopeless-

ness deepened general morality was undermined" (Caudill, 1963, p. 285). The helplessness of the male, was then translated into the abuse of the ADC system, by the "fertile and amoral females [residing] in every camp and on every creek." As Caudill wrote, "the sexual mores of the mountaineer were never strict [to begin with]... [as] they have taken a practical attitude toward sex and quite unashamedly behave as nature guides them....[and] this tolerant attitude.... brought about an amazing reaction when the public assistance program began to dispense hard cash for the support of illegitimate children..." (Caudill, 1963, pp. 286-87).

Out of wedlock children were not seriously rejected or scorned, and before the public assistance program, the woman used to "swear out a bastardy warrant" for the father, seek him out, and sue him to pay for the child's support. This, according to the author, was a more preferable arrangement, despite the fact that fathers were unemployed and financially helpless. The assistance program, according to him, encouraged the "wronged mother" instead to report that the father was unknown, resorting even more to "illicit associations, illegitimate children and the certainty of welfare checks in preference to the uncertainty of the holy but penniless state of matrimony." Thus, as stated in passages underlined by Moynihan, "in the poverty ridden Cumberlands, the ADC program has in great part been allowed to degenerate into a system of subsidies calculated to perpetuate and multiply immorality" (Caudill, 1963, p. 287). One other detail in these pages was about the alarming rate in which high school educated young women were leaving the plateau, never coming back to set an example for the remaining adolescent girls who were "less ambitious, and frequently of lesser mentality." Thus, unlike their male counterparts who were trapped in this cycle, looking for and being unable to find any local or out-of-state job opportunities, these women were able to escape. However,

their moving up in the socio-economic ladder, added onto the societal vicious cycle of unemployed males, amoral “welfare mothers” and illegitimate children.

Caudill’s book had a very important policy implication, along with Michael Harrington’s *The Other America* (1962) published at about the same time, in inspiring the Kennedy administration for committing to a program to fight poverty. Although Harrington’s book conveyed a different message, both dealt with a lower-class subculture that fed on itself. The “culture of poverty” thesis, proposed by Oscar Lewis’s *Five Families: Mexican Case Studies in the Culture of Poverty* (1959), had actually been given a structural hint with Harrington’s, who also attracted attention to the urban slums. All these paradigm-changing studies had defined a “new poverty,” which had been subject to generations of economic hardship and eventually ended up being trapped in a whole different world invisible to the affluent middle class, and independent from the nation’s overall economic growth. And with more studies in mid 1960s, this “new poverty” was increasingly becoming about an even newer kind of poor – black and urban – but with the same crisis ridden and gendered arguments. In the process, the focus escaped even more away from structural explanations and remedies, to cultured and more importantly gendered ones, if not out rightly racialized. Thus, the “fertile and amoral female” subject of Caudill, became the constant for both mainstream scholars of poverty, and policy makers like Moynihan (Caudill, 1963, pp. 286-87).

Moreover, the conflation of the rural poverty of an earlier era with its more contemporary urban counterpart seemed to amplify both the racial and gendered element. The image of Cumberlands was easily projected into the new urban and mostly “racial” face of the problem, especially by the social scientist trying to achieve concrete policy outcomes for the new era. One notable example in this regard was the 1963 meeting of the National Poverty Committee on

Pockets of Poverty and the report, *Poverty in America* that resulted from this study and released before the Economic Opportunity Act was sent to Congress ("Affluent Society Breeds," 1963; see Footnote 7). The study was conducted under the auspices of National Farmers Union's Farmers Educational Foundation and the committee was chaired by NFU's James G. Patton.⁷ As the title of the committee suggested, the eventual report was mainly about "the pockets of poverty" – the committee adopted the term 'pockets of poverty,' a concept famously articulated in John Kenneth Galbraith's *The Affluent Society* (1958). Indeed, the opening address at the meeting of the committee was by Galbraith, and James G. Patton announced in the press release for the study, the existence of a "new class of Americans" isolated from "our Affluent Society" whose plight worsened when economy goes down, but nonetheless remained unaffected by an overall economic uplift. As quoted from the report, the "new class" here, the product of the kind of poverty referred to by Lewis, Harrington, and Caudill earlier, was actually a confluence of the new urban poor - "non-whites, families with no earners, families whose heads are females, males aged 14 to 25 or over 65" - and "those with less than eight years of education, inhabitants of rural farm areas, and families in which there are more than six children under 18..." Although priority tended to remain on the urban space, both social scientific discourse wise in the 1960s and in terms of policy implementations, the idea that the poor would always be the rural poor with a whole different set of cultural traits, transplanted into the urban atmosphere with migration and modernization, seemed to remain constant, carrying old prejudices to the new geography. This transfer, also encouraged the transfer, and even amplification of racialized and gendered prejudices. Meanwhile, no matter how structural the analysis was, the policy recommendations happened to be far from structural. The prejudices of an earlier tradition

7 Subsequent references to these documents from the National Policy Committee on Pockets of Poverty are cited by their specific titles and dates as found in the Moynihan Papers.

of poverty research regarding the poor, seemed to be projected into the new one with the same use of language. Apart from the fact that this language reflected an earlier tendency to assume an isolated culture pertaining to lower class, it also avoided phrases directly evoking any sort of wealth redistribution. The press release made mention of 20 million “abject poor in America who live *below subsistence standards*” without noting any clear economic categorization of income levels (“Affluent Society Breeds,” 1963).

All these tendencies were also evident in Galbraith’s opening speech at the initial committee meeting (“Affluent Society Breeds,” 1963, p. 7) The way he defined poverty was making clear that what he meant by structural conditions – the conditions that imprisonment certain parts of the population in enclaves of poverty – were reasons of “location, education, health, environment in youth or mental deficiency, or...of racial discrimination.” Low income was not stated among the root causes for why the poor “could not participate in the economic life of the nation” and racism was only stated lastly. As the problem was rooted in these seemingly structural fields, which were in fact the outcomes of economic inequality, the remedies were sought here. Arguing against the case favoring “a steady expansion in economic output... [and] a broad and equitable distribution of the revenues from production,” which he announced would merely lead to rewarding the rich, he explained the real subject in any attempt at alleviating poverty:

If the head of a family is stranded deep on the Cumberland Plateau, or if he never went to school, or if he has no useful skill, or if his health is broken, or if he succumbed as a youngster to a slum environment, or if opportunity is denied to him because he is a Negro then he will be poor and his family will be poor and that will be true no matter how opulent everyone becomes (“Affluent Society Breeds,” 1963, p. 2).

Along with drawing a picture of the "pockets of poverty" not merely in economic but socio-cultural terms, this statement also projected the image of the poor subject to be rescued from an insulated space. More importantly, the subject to be rescued was a man, either white and rural, or black and urban, who was destined to take the following generation down if the cycle was not broken from the outside. Here the confluence, evident in Patton's announcements, revealed itself with the young male as the ultimate victim and the one to be rescued in the first place. As Galbraith explained, "the means for rescuing this man, or his children...[would] require public efforts and public funds" ("Affluent Society Breeds," 1963, p. 2). In fact, this gendered view of the middle-class nuclear family ideal was a very important and rhetorically useful element for the ease at which scholars and policy makers could discuss economic inequality without directly attacking the income gap, and in most cases, racial discrimination.

Announced in March 5, 1964 with a press release by the committee, to be the "most comprehensive and authoritative of its kind yet made public," its report *Poverty in America* was also one of the earliest to make the scholarly language of crisis public ("National Policy Committee Issues Report," 1964). The report was written by Oscar Ornati, committee member and a professor of economics of the New School for Social Research, and the study it depended on was funded by the Twentieth Century Fund. The committee's emphasis on linking rural poverty to the new problem of urban youth was evident in this opinions piece. As it stated, "the plight of still another group [other than, the rural poor and the aged] – young people coming into the labor market – has been greatly aggravated by the recent rapid increase which has taken place in industrial productivity" ("National Policy Committee Issues Report," 1964, p. 6). It warned that the recent increase in productivity owing to automation was expected to continue and

affect workers of all ages, but with a much heavier burden on the youth entering the market without any work experience. Looking at the “poverty-linked attributes” listed in the report, it was also clear that the most problematic population group would be the black and urban families, headed by females, and thus their poorly educated and too many children. The summary of the report made public in this press release, listed a series of attributes, each defined and evaluated in their own terms. All these attributes were in line with the earlier definition of the new kind of poverty that Galbraith had borrowed from Patton in his address to the committee meeting. Dismissing the idea of trying to count the poor merely by looking at the income levels, and without paying specific attention to the way they are grouped or the way they live, as required by the then newly popularizing “poverty line” approach devised by Mollie Orshansky of the Social Security Administration, the report instead aimed to sort out all possible complex variables. According to Ornati, “far more important than a count of the poor [was] the identification of groups that are poor and of the relative risk of poverty individuals incur because of conditions...beyond their control.” The reasoning that he stated was behind this approach was twofold, both of which clearly had policy implications in mind: firstly, the idea that searching for a consensus on the meaning of poverty would delay policy action, and secondly the idea that “viewing poverty as the condition of large but ill defined populations [would not] give policy guidance” and specific programs aimed at specific individuals. (Ornati, 1964, p. 2) This attempt at defining the afflicted population, and thus categorizing it, brought about the most important “poverty-linked attribute” as being non-white, being a farmer, being aged, and being a female head of a family. The report stated that

Poverty is no longer a condition, which strikes all kinds of individuals but rather tends to charac-

terize the great majority of individuals in certain large 'poverty-linked' groups. If a family is in one of these groups, the probabilities are that it will be poor regardless of how poverty is defined. Poverty is revealed to be the usual product of certain social, economic, and geographical conditions. For a family with such 'poverty-linked' characteristics, rare escapes from poverty require the unusual combination of great ability, hard-work, good luck, and an exceptionally prosperous economy. ("National Policy Committee Issues Report," 1964, p. 2)

Developing on Galbraith's pockets of poverty thesis, the Ornati report detailed the composition of these enclaves by grouping families according to their poverty-linked characteristics, which were definitive of the new poor. As noted earlier, these were characteristics such as being non-white, being from families with no earners, being from families headed by females, being male and young, being over 65, being uneducated, residing in a rural farm area, being from a family with more than six children under 18, and residing in the South. The study's aim was to determine these characteristics – the problem of overlap notwithstanding and stated as its limitation – and "simply examine[d] the extent to which low income population consist[ed] of people with such characteristics" (Ornati, 1964, p. 3). The reasoning for this was the idea that since World War II, poverty had become "increasingly a burden carried by 'special' groups and individuals." According to the report, before that, almost all "shared in the national insufficiency" and regardless of whether one was black or a female family head or southern, "many without these attributes shared their fate" and all had a chance to move out through hard work. In the 1960s America however, the report argued, poverty was to be dealt with more properly, "in terms of programs necessary to improve conditions in which certain groups live, and of the *characteristics which they possess* [my italics]." The convergence of these characteristics, which was

often the case (though the majority of the poor came from families with just one poverty-linked attribute), created “multi-problem” or “multi-characteristic” families, whose most damaging attribute was “being non-white.” (Ornati, 1964, p. 10)

The ultimate policy suggestion that both this report, and the studies conducted and meetings held in its preparation, was education aimed specifically at this new problem population comprised of certain specific groups, in their view, seriously cut off from the rest of the affluence of the decade, because of “conditions beyond their control.” (Ornati, 1964, p. 2) Those conditions, however, never directly made mention of racial discrimination, income gap and economic inequality. It was as if both the academia and the policy makers, were trying hard to redefine the problem, within the post-war and Cold War context, in which mention of the inherent economic inequalities or mention of class differences strictly in the economic sense, would no longer have an attentive audience. In line with the policy tendencies of both the Kennedy and the Johnson administrations, what most studies pointed to were rehabilitative educational programs and services aimed at the children of the “multi-problem” families. It seemed that the most widely shared concern the early 1960s sociologist and economists was the assumption that the poverty problem that they faced was a whole different and much more multifaceted and complicated sort – a new poverty need to be approached with new tools – culture being the most utilized. No matter how structurally they organized certain “features,” “characteristics,” “attributes,” or “conditions,” the “culture of poverty” idea seemed to hover above every economic and sociological study. The most important outcome of this tendency revealed itself in inevitably racialized and gendered premises, and when doubled with the post war scholarly heritage of interest in the issues of sexuality, child rearing, and the family, both scholars and policy makers, and scholar-politicians like

Moynihan, sought the policy solutions to poverty in these fields.⁸

A New Kind of Approach for the Complexity of "The Black Boy Crisis"

Daniel Geary had tackled the issue of racial liberalism and the policy impact of the Moynihan Report and noted its "gender conservatism" in his 2011 *Daedalus* article "Racial Liberalism, the Moynihan Report & the Dædalus Project on 'The Negro American,'"⁹ before his in-depth analysis in *Beyond Civil Rights* (2015) (Geary, 2011; see Footnote 9). According to Geary, the fact that Lyndon B. Johnson's Howard University speech was based on the report and that Moynihan coauthored the speech after attending two Dædalus conferences "indicates the direct connections between the intellectual and political dimensions of racial liberalism's socioeconomic turn in the mid-1960s" (Geary, 2011, p. 55). Attracting attention to the gender makeup of the Dædalus conference, being "almost exclusively male" he pinpointed at this as the reason that the major criticism concerning its patriarchal assumptions were not sufficiently voiced during the conference (Geary, 2011, p. 60). Citing Feldstein (2000), he noted that in 1965, most liberals and many civil rights leaders still thought within a family-wage framework ...[and the]discussion at the conference revolved almost entirely around what could be done for black men, who....were seen as suffering the brunt of economic and psychological oppression. Conference participants frequently used the pronoun "he" to refer to "the Negro." When African American women were discussed, their relative economic success in comparison with black men was depicted as a threat to the restoration of black manhood and hence to progress toward racial equality. For example, Moynihan recounted that efforts to hire African Americans in his own government department in recent years had benefited black women to

8 Such policy initiatives as the Head Start, HARYOU, and Mobilization for Youth can be seen in this respect.

9 This issue, entitled "Race in the Age of Obama, Volume 1" was one of the two issues dedicated to race and equality in 2011. The other was the Spring issue entitled "Race, Inequality, & Culture, Volume 2." This issue is reminiscent of the two issues devoted to the "Negro Problem" back in 1965 and 1966, and thus can be seen as another instant where the Moynihan report's legacy had been revived again in the 21st century. Moynihan was among the contributors of that earlier *Daedalus* project, which is the subject of Geary's article in question. See reference list for said issues of *Daedalus*.

the detriment of black men: “You can stand in front of the Department of Labor any morning at eight-thirty, and it is a sight: spectacularly well-dressed, competent, beautiful [black] young women . . . spending the day on the phone with the Attorney General and seeing ambassadors, then coming home and asking the old man, what did you do today?” (Geary, 2011, p. 61)

The Dædalus project was basically a set of two conferences, two journal issues, and a book that came out in 1966. Johnson had written a foreword for an issue and Moynihan had contributed to the special issue with what Geary called “the scholarly twin” of his controversial report – an article entitled “Employment, Income, and the Ordeal of the Negro Family.” He had written this piece at about the same time he was writing the report intent on shaping government policy and as Geary argued, it “was a political document that drew heavily on social-scientific ideas; [and] rarely have politics and scholarship come so closely together.” And, “the Dædalus project [itself] was a key conduit for introducing social-scientific knowledge into government policy-making and, ultimately, public controversy” (Geary, 2011, pp. 53–54). The first session of the first day of the formal conference that made up this project, gave the start in May 14, 1965, with the Dædalus editor Stephen R. Graubard’s introduction. It is revealing to note that Graubard commenced the session at that important historical moment by announcing “that we might properly begin with three of the papers which are among the most provocative we have, those of Mr. [Rashi] Fein, Mr. [Philip M.] Hauser, and Mr. Moynihan.” And at the interruption of one of the participants, he added to the debate a fourth paper by James Tobin (“Transcript of the American Academy Conference,” 1966, p. 287; see also “Back Matter,” 1965 for biographical information on the participants). Commencing just a few months after Moynihan completed his report (that was in March),

and just a few months before the series of events that would push him away from Washington back to academia and back to his work on *Toward Equality*, this two-day conference was historically situated at just a crucial stage.¹⁰ A few months after the conference, Lyndon Johnson would address Howard University with the historic speech, whose text was partly based on the report. However, late in that summer, riots in Watts would break out; the Report would leak to the press at about the same time with immense popularity and controversy; and Moynihan would leave his post in the Department of Labor. By the time the second special issue of *Dædalus* and thus the transcript of the conference was printed in the winter of 1966, Moynihan was at Wesleyan University's Center for Advanced Studies. In a couple of months, he would become the director of the Harvard-MIT Joint Center for Urban Studies (Hodgson, 2000, pp. 108–114). Thus the *Dædalus* project, stood at an important juncture in many ways, most important of which for the inquiry undertaken here, is what Geary referred to its being a "key conduit for introducing social-scientific knowledge into government" at such a historic moment.

Not only the content but also the authorship of the three other papers that Graubard chose to stress in the same framework with Moynihan's in opening the discussion, were noteworthy. Rashi Fein, an economist and a former staff at the Council of Economic Advisers, was a Senior Staff at the Brookings Institution. Philip M. Hauser was a Professor of Sociology and Director of the Population Research and Training Center of the University of Chicago. James Tobin was a Professor of Economics at Yale University and, like Fein, was a former member of the CEA. And Moynihan, was still the Assistant Secretary of Labor ("Back Matter," 1965). Apart from the domination of the bunch by economists and those with government experience, one common thread that linked their papers first was their skepticism about the pro-

10 In July of 1965, Moynihan would resign from his post at the Department of Labor, to become the director of Harvard-MIT Joint Center for Urban Studies.

gress in the realm of racial equality ("Transcript of the American Academy Conference," 1966, p. 287). More importantly however, Graubard declared that, all of them

pay particular heed to the grave problems created by high unemployment and unstable family structure. The poverty of the Negro family, Mr. Hauser says, must rank as the single most important factor preventing the Negro from achieving his potential so that he is able to assume the rights and obligations proper to a first-class American citizen. The point made by Mr. Moynihan (and supported by Mr. [John B.] Turner) is that it is imperative that we give immediate attention to the problems of Negro youth and of the Negro male worker ("Transcript of the American Academy Conference," 1966, pp. 287-288)¹¹

¹¹ John B. Turner, was a Professor of Social Work at the School of Applied Social Sciences of Western Reserve University and consultant to the National Urban League. See "Back Matter" (1965).

Graubard then went on to stress the immediacy of the agenda, by presenting James Tobin's paper. Evident of the confluence of socioeconomic and cultural concerns in policy circles, the three "absolutely essential" points that Tobin's paper made were; first, that unemployment was the key problem, second, that the federal government should do more about it... "[and] third, that we ought to reconsider our welfare programs. These welfare policies, so largely constructed, I suspect, out of the ideas and experience of the 1930's, are simply not, in the context of the 1960's, producing the social order that we want to see" ("Transcript of the American Academy Conference," 1966, p. 288).

The two immediate concerns about the plight of the black man and about the need to take immediate action in reforming welfare policies in that light, came together in this opening session. Tobin's idea that the new poverty was a multifaceted and a much more complicated problem, than its prewar counterpart, coupled with the tendency to see the behavior of the black man as the problem, pushed its analyzers for more "holistic and inter-disciplinary approach-

es".¹² Especially after his report came under attack from the left, Moynihan probably intended to do so, leaving this conference with the idea that there is a substantial amount of consensus in academic, civil rights, and government circles, for the way he treated the problem in his paper. Considering Moynihan's already existing interest in family issues, the available literature that was a follow up of the Cold War interest in sexuality and masculinity, especially in psychiatry was one useful pool of data for such sought-for interdisciplinary approach.

The studies filed under his readings as he worked towards his never published work *Towards Equality*, revealed the most illustrating examples of such scholarship. In a letter dated March 1966, as he was working on the book which, he wrote, was "about the implications for public policy of the problems of lower class Negro American families," Moynihan wrote to Dr. Bertram S. Brown of the National Institute of Mental Health, inquiring about further details regarding his work on the IQ levels of imprisoned people (Brown, 1966). Saying that exactly a year ago, as he was working on his own report of the black family, he had been "immensely impressed" by the preliminary report issued after this mental health survey Brown had conducted with Dr. Thomas F. Coutless, from the Institute of Law, Psychiatry and Criminology at George Washington University Law Center, and David E. Silber, assistant Professor of Psychology at George Washington University. This brief letter, revealed his continued interest in the plight of the urban black male and the psychiatric implications involved. He lamented to Dr. Brown, that the world of his subjects – that of "the lower class Negro families" – was

...of course, desperately afflicted by crime and "borderline" intelligence. I have some data which would indicate rather more than half the adult Negro males in New York City have been in prison (sentenced or detained). Similarly,

12 This expression is attributed to Edgar H. Auerswald, M.D., who used it in a paper shared with Moynihan. This paper, along with their subsequent correspondence, is analyzed in detail in the following sections (see pp. 71–79).

Roberts at Fisk [Dr. S. Oliver Roberts, a Fisk University psychologist], has just come up with results showing that the median I.Q. of Negro boys from broken families declines to 76 at age 10. Just how, and whether these fit together is a troubled subject indeed, but your research could provide an immensely suggestive connection. I would therefore greatly appreciate hearing of any progress you may have made, particularly as it might apply to Negroes (Brown, 1966).

The preliminary report he was referring to was to be presented two years later at the 1968 Annual meeting of the American Psychiatric Association, as the result of scholars in law, criminology, psychiatry, and psychology. Such interest in the mental plight of the black boy and its connection to the post-war political and intellectual context, was also evident in many other studies Moynihan reserved for applying to in the course of his research in preparation of *Toward Equality*. The disparity between the educational achievement of black male and female youth, closely connected to the issue of the intellectual and mental failure of the black male, would be one very dominant theme of the Moynihan Report. In all studies he had at his disposal analyzing low-income black urban families, through such issues of illegitimacy, emasculation, delinquency, mental retardation (all terms as they were used back then,) the “black boy crisis” that historian Lindquist referred to was the overarching theme (Lindquist, 2012).

It was as if the post-war arguments around “momism” and emasculation of white middle class suburban boys, had a continuing strand in the scholarship that tried to come to grips with this new kind of poverty. And as it was with the post-war literature, the real intent was saving the victimized male – this time, lower-class, black and urban – suffering at the expense of either educationally successful sisters or dominant mothers.

The biggest concern was about this new generation

to come – "the children of hard-core urban families." The phrasing was from the title of another study in Moynihan's file of materials for *Toward Equality*. It was one of the many papers that Moynihan requested personally from Edgar H. Auerswald, the Clinical Director of the Wiltwyck School for Boys. As Auerswald noted in the letter in which he enclosed the works he compiled, he was "attempting to pull these observations together into a paper on the origins of violence in the cities" (Auerswald, 1967). The letter was dated to the fall of 1967, the aftermath of the urban race riots, and the earliest study he attached to his letter as the basis for the ones that followed, was the one based on observations from the Wiltwyck School¹³, which was a paper presented at the March 1964 convention of the American Orthopsychiatric Association (Auerswald, 1964).

The paper opened up with the story of Kenny, an eight-year-old boy who stood with his mother on the bench of the Children's Court for the third time. He had been caught stealing in a dime store, a few days after being suspended from his second grade class. "An alert, bright boy, although his I.Q. [didn't] show," Kenny had four siblings living with his mother in a tenement house. His older brother was already in the State Training School, and also included in the family was a baby, the out-of-wedlock child of his fourteen-year-old sister. Kenny was himself an out-of-wedlock child, whose father, "a proud but unskilled man," was living elsewhere trying to contribute a few dollars to the family "when and if he can find menial work which is seldom" (Auerswald, 1964). As Auerswald warned, this family had been known to many service agencies including the Department of Welfare, and for years,

...teachers, principals, guidance counselors, welfare workers, probation officers, social workers, psychologist, and psychiatrists have lectured, cajoled, bribed, nurtured, supported, fathered, and psychotherapized him and other members

13 Founded in 1936, the school was located in Esopus, New York. Initially designed as an "experimental summer camp for Protestant African-American juvenile delinquents and potential juvenile delinquents" the school expanded to include "to include children and adolescents with severe emotional disturbances" in 1953 when a group of reformers including Judge Justine Polier Wise and Eleanor Roosevelt showed interest in the institution. For a detailed history and a description of the school's archival records, see the Columbia University Libraries finding aid at http://www.columbia.edu/cu/lweb/archival/collections/ldpd_6262245/

of his family...[with] messages containing the values and requirements of social living in our larger society. Somehow these messages have not been heard. A curious refractory wall seems to prevent Kenny and his family from receiving them (Auerswald, 1964, p. 2).

According to Auerswald, Kenny, and many like him, were like “aliens in a new country,” as they came from “Michael Harrington’s ‘Other America,’ from James Baldwin’s ‘Another Country,’ from slums, from ghettos, from the concrete jungles of our inner cities, and the gray shacks on the other side of the tracks...from families who have lived for generations under the crush of poverty, where survival is the main theme of life, where pleasure is where you find it, where no one gives a damn about the Joneses” (Auerswald, 1964, p. 2). It was a world, defined as a “splinter society” whose “structure and operational content” and “the line of development” that the families within it had taken, had turned into an alien field “outside the awareness of [currently available] disciplines” (Auerswald, 1964, p. 3). Auerswald, like most of the early 1960s social scientists, acknowledged the presence of a “sense of crisis” about this “expanding segment of people and families, whose needs will not be met despite the external provisions...of our democratic state.” “The full appraisal of this other society,” he warned, would not be made neither through a study “emanating from any single discipline,” nor any “simple combination of disciplinary approaches in the behavioral sciences” (Auerswald, 1964, p. 3). This new “splinter society,” and the adults and their children living in it, were perceived as an alien occurrence for which no fitting disciplinary framework was yet developed. This study on a group of boys from Wiltwyck and their families, was an attempt at such a framework.

Basing its theoretical premises on the influential Harvard sociologist Talcott Parsons’ designation of the family as the major socializing unit, and its practical

ones, on the idea that "residential treatment" would be best suited to the "process of total family habilitation;" the paper eventually provided, as Auerswald put it, "a new pair of glasses with which to look at all of the families of children referred to Wiltwyk, particularly those who [came] from the 'other society.'" (Auerswald, 1964, p. 5) This "new pair of glasses" was a set of twin and interdependent concepts; first being a "reality differentiation" – an extension of psychologist Herman Witkin's "psychological differentiation" – and second, "personality integration" (Auerswald, 1964, pp. 7-8). In order to develop sufficient "reality differentiation to assure his effective adaptation to the large variety of life situations, the pre-school child depended on the proper reception of as numerous and as clearly articulated "integrating themes" from his family as possible, and with the right timing for each theme (Auerswald, 1964, p. 10). In order to elaborate on the importance of the mother in this equation, Auerswald referred to W. Goldfarb and D. Meyer's concept of "maternal perplexity," where the child developed in a vacuum, devoid of integrating themes because of the way the mother was "paralyzed in her responses to the child," either by not responding at all or responding in a chaotic and unthematic manner (Auerswald, 1964, p. 11). According to Auerswald, the way these scholars had labeled boys who were acting-out as "schizophrenic," although their sample were "without organic deficit," was one example of how the field was not yet competent in analyzing such children and their family situations. Such chaotic and "undifferentiated behavior" on part of the parents (mostly mothers), who were themselves "undifferentiated people" with few "integrating themes," happened when they were "confronted with situations which [were] too complex and unfamiliar to be met with their limited armamentarium of coping responses" (Auerswald, 1964, pp. 12-13). At such moments, which were probably numerous as the outside world was one of con-

stant change and progress, the parent would, after a “period of functional paralysis,” “begin to disorganize” and the level of tension in the parent, actually not related to the child, would form some form of violent response, unpredictable to the child (Auerswald, 1964, p. 13). That, in turn, would create children, able to communicate through a language of violence only. Auerswald, also added that, in the ever changing and ever more complex society, “the state of affairs ha[d] become self-perpetuating,” as such families with “undifferentiated parents” were “rapidly producing” more poorly equipped children, prone to violence and delinquent behavior.

Auerswald concluded this paper, in line with its aspirations, with a note on the need for new ways of categorizing such problem families. The sense of crisis expressed in this paper, was also evident in another one, presented at the previous year’s annual meeting, again that of the American Orthopsychiatric Association, in 1963. This time the study was collaboration between Auerswald and three other colleagues – Salvador Minuchin, a renowned family therapist, leading the field of structural family therapy; Charles H. King, the executive director of Wiltwyck, who would later be the executive director of Haryou-Act in 1967; and Clara Rabinowitz, a social worker, again from the Wiltwyck team (Minuchin et al., 1963). In the note handwritten (probably by Moynihan’s assistant) on the cover page of the paper entitled “The Study and Treatment of Families Who Produce Multiple Acting-out Boys,” special markings on the paper were explained for Moynihan’s interest: sections marked “A” were said to “describe ingredients of family life that produce people who [were] inevitably drawn to contribute to a stance of ‘black power’ and violence;” and the places marked with “B” were “a significant contribution to the difficulties in maintaining a meaningful problem-solving dialogue with ‘poverty groups’” (Minuchin et al., 1963).

Marked with "A" were the stories of two sample families. One was a Puerto Rican family, with a "bright, verbal, alcoholic, phobic" father "given to shifting from excessive love to excessive rage," and a "slow and depressed" mother "with psychosomatic symptoms, suicidal idea, and chronic resentment." They had four children – a ten-year-old girl "showing psychosomatic symptoms and depression," two elder brothers who already show "acting-out behavior," and a boy of three, "a delightful hyperactive youngster" (Minuchin et al., 1963, pp. 4-5) The focus of the observation was the relationship between the parents and the youngest boy, who seemed to be on the same track as his two elder brothers. According to the observations, he was subjected to some kind of violent reaction from the parents, repetitively and at unpredictable moments. Testing the "limit of the permissible," he would go on acting-out again and again, which the parents would dismiss with "lack of reactivity." This lack of response was, as Auerswald emphasized several times in the paper, "seemed to be related to the internal stress of the parents and not the action of the child." When the child wanted to "acknowledge himself as the doer,...as existing," after repetitively acting out, the response he eventually got was a violent one. He would be torn between no response at all or a "violent, capricious, and incomprehensible" one, and nothing in between these two extremes (Minuchin et al., 1963, p. 6). As Auerswald explained, this resulted in the child's inability to relate his experience meaningfully to what was happening to him, seriously impairing his sense of self and causing him to always be in "search for extreme dramatic stimulation." According to him, "it is as if the stimulation must be multiplied before it is intense enough to make the child perceive that 'this is happening to me' rather than 'around me' ... [which explained] the need for danger and adventure, and for much of the senseless cruelty often displayed in 'delinquent' behavior" (Minuchin et al., 1963, p. 7).

Another problematic form of interaction that explained this kind of tendency for violence and aggression was what Auerswald called “the nurturing transaction.” It was basically the parents’ exaggerated reliance of their function as nurturers and givers. When this role was not fulfilled, and a demand on part of the child was not met, the parent perceived it as a personal failure and lost self-esteem, “for a variety of reasons stemming from [their] cultural and experiential background.” This sense of guilt would be projected in the child as a feeling that he had a right to everything, and thus a lack of the sense of guilt – mostly exemplified with the act of stealing, for which he felt he had “simply repaired an injustice.” Although Auerswald noted that both parents had the same tendency, the way the mother responded to this sense of guilt in certain ways was what complicated things, and eventually caused destructive tendencies in the child. It was the mother, whose “communication [was] full of variations of the theme...[with conflicting messages to the child such as] ‘You should help me, but you make me sick instead,’ and ‘I try my best but I am helpless and cannot control you’.” This according to Auerswald, caused the child to “incorporate a self-image of evil omnipotence” and together with the conflicting feelings of devotion to her protection and fear of harming her and losing her. Then Auerswald went on to explain how this could be a reason behind the quest of power (the word underlined on the text, to emphasize the link to “black power” as noted in the handwritten note on the cover page):

Thus the child is subjected to conflicting simultaneous messages, “You are helpless and dependent on my nurturance for survival” and, “You have the power to hurt or destroy me, you source of survival.” Here are two contradictory messages, which simultaneously label the child as powerful and as weak. He cannot integrate such opposites. To avoid disorganization he seems to select the message with most survival value,

namely, that which offers *power* [underlined] rather than helplessness (Minuchin et al., 1963, p. 8).

In a later work by Auerswald, published in 1966 at the height of the urban riots, this link between the psychological intra-family dynamics, especially between the mother and child (male), and the quest for power and violence on part of the urban male youth, was even more evident (Auerswald, 1966). However, this tendency in the scholarship was already evident early in the decade, as illustrated most clearly by a 1963 study on crime, contained in the same folder as Auerswald's works (Bacon et al., 1965). Funded by grants from the Social Science Research Council, the Ford Foundation and the NIMH, it was collaboration between psychologists and anthropologists from Yale University, trying a cross-cultural approach, to observe "a great variety of cultural conditions instead of being limited to a single cultural setting" (Bacon et al., 1965, p. 80). Working on a sample from 48 different societies from over the world, the study looked into the hypothesis that "crime arises partly as a defense mechanism against strong feminine identification" for the need for expressing a "compulsive masculinity" in later stages of the lives of most lower-class males raised in lower class homes (Bacon et al., 1965, p. 81).

Such tendency to explain society at large, in strictly gendered terms, and the association of this particular way of living with the black urban poor, would increasingly reveal itself even more directly in the works published within the context of or in the aftermath of the urban riots – a time when the controversy over the leaking of the Moynihan Report would also arise, in both intellectual and political circles. The earlier mentioned paper of Auerswald, was an example at point. Presented at a graduate conference in Yeshiva University in 1966, it was a restatement of his earlier findings around ideas of "reality differentiation," "integrating themes," the challenges of the

increasing complexity of the environmental changes taking place in the context of rapid urbanization, and the need to develop a “more holistic theory of cognitive development” (Auerswald, 1966, pp. 1–6). However, as the title “Cognitive Development and Psychopathology in the Urban Environment” suggested, this time the findings mentioned in the previous study on crime and its links to what was happening in the urban centers was more clearly stated, together with the racial implications. And this time, Auerswald, clearly noted the broader political and social implications as well. A child (male), reared in the kind of “undifferentiated” problem families he had described earlier, and thus with “relatively few ‘integrating themes’ which are concurrent with and rooted in societal values, institutions, and laws... [would be] devoid of knowledge of the expectations placed on him as a citizen and a member of society” (Auerswald, 1966, p. 14). This individual, according to Auerswald, would be unable to verbalize his concept of himself and would tend to resort to emotions of fear and rage, with instincts for survival. “This hypothetical child-adolescent,” as Auerswald named his subject, would then tend to “band with others... [with] the same developmental arrest...[and] drift with them as they collectively seek gratifications of primitive pleasure needs and high level stimuli and activities” to provide him with a momentary meaning for life. His usual social environment, his neighborhood, was a place where he would always find a “peer with delinquent values...to organize a fighting gang, where the narcotics pusher or illicit vendor of drugs [was] in open operation, or where the soap box agitator or the igniting incident amidst racial or social tensions [could] easily incite a mob to violence” (Auerswald, 1966, p. 15). In concluding the paper, Auerswald criticized the War on Poverty, and all its schools – the opportunity school advocating job creation and better housing, the school advising job training programs, the one advocating

training in neighborhood service centers, and finally the early childhood education group having inspired the Headstart program. According to him, all these schools were bound to fail as a whole new "curriculum for living" needed to be devised, in order to cope with the challenges of delivering a "differentiating experience to this group," by means of organizing all the various agencies of teachers, welfare workers, or probation officers "in a total community effort," under the guidance and leadership of educators – biological and behavioral scientists collaborating. This was the only way, he thought, it would be possible to decrease the number of "ready made rioters in a community" and thus the "vandalism and senseless rioting and destruction (Auerswald, 1966, pp. 17–22).

To Conclude: How, Actually, Was Sociological Research on Poverty Marginalized?

The kinds of resources Moynihan utilized during his research for *Toward Equality*, which lasted roughly until his appointment to the Nixon administration, is revealing despite the fact that Moynihan never published the book. Focusing on Moynihan's readings from this period, demonstrated how he found the means for defending his stance in the report, with a variety of studies, that could be stretched, school and approach-wise, back to the post-war era's masculinity and manhood centered social science.

Going back to one of the broader questions that this article was initially informed by; it was obvious that the kind of research done here – in the manner of a "mass intellectual" as Sanford F. Schram attuned to Moynihan – was made more relevant simply because it was made in "the halls of power," independent of the scientific quality about the arguments made. The reason behind the marginalization of the discipline of sociology in particular, about which Katz (2013), Schram (2002), and O'Connor (2001) were all discomforted, seemed to be less about the insufficiency

of the efforts of or the fallacy of the methodology of such scholar activists as Piven and Cloward (1971), but more about the all-encompassing gendered and racialized mindset and language of the mid-1960s. One of the most obvious instances, in Moynihan's story, that made such an impression was a brief correspondence found in his papers at the LOC. On March 5, 1966, social psychologist Thomas Pettigrew, wrote from Harvard's Department of Social Relations, to Daniel Patrick Moynihan, for consolation:

Dear Pat,

All I can say is: Who the hell is "Laura Carper"? These creatures – Carper, Ryan, etc. – seem to continually come crawling out from under their rocks – and magazines...continue to publish the bilge – ignorant and vicious as it may be.

....

At any rate, I sympathize with you – and I trust your new book will mention the easy exploitation by the uninformed of our presumably "left" press... (Pettigrew, 1966)

When Moynihan received this letter, the Moynihan Report, was at its peak. The context of the urban riots, exploding right after the Report was leaked to the press back in the late summer of 1965, had added an additional fervor to the public and scholarly debate. As to "Who the hell Laura Carper was": she was one of the many early feminist critics, whose take on the controversy did not find much publicity back in the day despite its soundness. Both the mainstream press and mainstream academia, did not seem to be interested in such critique, may be until it became assertive enough late in the decade.

The liberal intellectuals and politicians of the mid-1960s, including Moynihan and Pettigrew, were rather interested in hastily reaching policy solutions to a perceived impending crisis awaiting the nation. Being attuned to what Robert Self has called "breadwinner liberalism," what mattered most for them

were breadwinners, and prospective breadwinners, on whose capabilities the whole socio-economic system seemed to depend. All the works that Moynihan chose to utilize, in the brief period that he spent in the academy between his two political posts, provides a glimpse into the kind of social science that the Great Society liberal politicians and intellectuals produced. Aiming for new solutions, for the profoundly changing and complicated times they had a difficulty of coming to grips with, they seemed to resort increasingly toward the line of knowledge produced back in the immediate post-war. With the same sense of fear and crisis, surrounding the theme of "momism" back then, they tended to look even much further than the underlying economic and racial inequalities of the times, despite ironically, their haste in achieving results by encouraging government action.

And in their hasty attempts at finding ways to restore the manhood of the problem black boy, they seemed to miss what less mainstream scientists and activists had to say. Belonging to the mainstream intellectual and academic circles, Moynihan and Pettigrew, did not seem to have much time to contemplate on what Laura Carper was trying to point at in her article. Published in March 1966 issue of the *Dissent Magazine*, her article did not only challenge Moynihan's "inappropriate" use of statistics and his "inappropriate approach" [in Frank Riessman's words, whose critique followed Carper's in the same issue], like most of the early critics of his report did (Riessman, 1966, p. 141). She pointed to something more fundamental when she also warned about the potential hazards of Moynihan's exaggerated emphasis on the need to restore the manhood of the black male, and save it from the so called matriarchal structure of the black families living in the urban ghettos. As Carper warned, "pathology was" actually "in the eye of the beholder," and the only policy solution that Moynihan seemed to offer in his report, was reminiscent of the problematic conception of masculinity that he

had (Carper, 1966, p. 139). According to Carper, “the desirability of army life,” as “a dramatic and desperately needed change: a world away from women... [was] patently absurd” (Carper, 1966, p. 140). It was not a masculine impotence rooted in history that inflicted him, but political, social and economic impotence caused by the contemporary state of affairs. What was destructive to the black man and woman was lack of social and economic power, “here and now.” Denying Moynihan’s analysis of a pathological heritage from days of slavery, she acclaimed that the black man, was “not grappling with the social system under which he lived over a hundred years ago, or even...ten years ago.” The challenge to the black community was political, whether it will be empowered was going to depend on whether “we can make room for the poor to acquire social and economic power” (Carper, 1966, p. 140).

Carper¹⁴ was a Michigan based scholar and activist, a member of the Michigan Civil Rights Commission, and as listed in the Directory of the U.S. Bureau of Apprenticeship and Training for reaching minority and women’s groups, she was the secretary of the Michigan Labor Committee for Human Rights by late 1970s. As Susan Greenbaum also noted in her book on the legacy of the Moynihan report, she was “labeled by detractors as a ‘feminist’,” after her critique appeared in the March 1966 issue of the *Dissent* magazine (U.S. Bureau of Apprenticeship and Training, 1979; Greenbaum, 2015, pp. 31–32; see Footnote 19). Included in her feminist critique was also concrete and from-the-field data offering an alternative explanation to Moynihan’s statistics of rising welfare rolls. As also rephrased in the May 1966 IRCD (Information Retrieval Center on the Disadvantaged) Bulletin of the U.S. Department of Health, Education, and Welfare, Carper observed how, in her own state of Michigan, “the welfare department which formerly denied assistance to applicants when there was evidence of poor housekeeping, mental disturbance, or

¹⁴ See *Directory for Reaching Minority and Women’s Groups* (Bureau of Apprenticeship and Training, 1979) and Greenbaum (2015, pp. 31–32). Carper’s essay was later anthologized in Rainwater and Yancey’s (1967) *The Moynihan Report and the Politics of Controversy*. Alongside Hylan Lewis and Herbert Gans, Carper’s work is frequently cited as one of the most significant critiques of the era (see Howard, 1968, p. 1191). The author wishes to thank Thomas J. Sugrue for his encouragement and guidance regarding further research into Laura Carper’s work.

of a male friend, granted aid in these types of cases, following legislative changes" (Goldberg, 1966).

The letter that Pettigrew sent Moynihan in consolation, right after Carper published in the *Dissent*, was one embodiment of the ways in which the gendered norms of the mid-1960s social science happened to marginalize a certain set of valuable feedback. One other such instant, more reflective of the racialized thinking that accompanied gendered assumptions, was at the earlier mentioned Dædalus conference. Ralph Ellison was the only black participant, as made obvious by Moynihan, and in the very few instances that he commented on the papers, he did so mostly in defense of the presence of a distinct black culture, which however proved rather successful in producing useful strategies and defense mechanisms in the highly discriminatory spirit of the times. As Geary also noted, he "challenged the unexamined value biases of social science itself...[by emphasizing the] white, middle-class, Protestant values and life style" that governed those values (Geary, 2011, p. 60).

At some point, after a lengthy discussion on possibilities of achieving full cultural adaptation of the black ghetto to the rest of American society, on what exactly the civil rights movement's seemingly conflicting demands were, and a final comment from Oscar Handlin that "the kind of community and the kind of organization that exist among Negroes are incomplete and fail to extend into a variety of areas, partly as a result of strategy and partly as a result of historical development," Ellison interrupted and exclaimed with the following remark:

One thing that is not quite clear to me is the implication that Negroes have come together and decided that we want to lose our identity as quickly as possible. Where does that idea come from? I have encountered it in a number of places recently. One place (which almost frightened the pants off me) was in *Commen-*

tary, where Mr. Nathan Glazer makes this assumption ...It is easy enough to see why Mr. Glazer would get off on that, because (as one of our participants also made very clear) he feels that Negroes have no culture...Sociologists often assert that there is a Negro thing? A timbre of a voice, a style, a rhythm? In all of its positive and negative implications, the expression of a certain kind of American uniqueness....If there is this uniqueness, why on earth would it not in some way be precious to the people who maintain it? (“Transcript of the American Academy Conference,” 1966, pp. 407–408)

In response, referring to Ellison’s mention of the book he co-authored with Glazer, *Beyond the Melting Pot*, Moynihan recounted his own experiences in growing up in New York as an Irish boy: “...I do think that the gentlemen of color in this room should remember that the experience of a great many of us in our life has not been so very different in some respects from yours. There have been differences, but the differences have been part of a spectrum. I grew up in Manhattan. Almost the first thing I learned was that we Irish were a put-upon, discriminated-against people” (“Transcript of the American Academy Conference,” 1966, p. 408).

The brief exchange of ideas evidenced in these two instances could be more than just a defensive posturing by 1960s intellectuals and even be more diagnostic, in answering questions regarding a proper relationship between social scientific research on poverty in the 1960s and political power, and regarding the marginalization of sociology as a discipline; than the sheer volume of archival data might suggest. Also, to ponder the “Moynihan Problem” today, without an understanding of the structural limitations of Great Society liberalism – especially, its gendered and racialized blind spots – would be to engage in incomplete history.

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